

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/43521516>

Cultural translation and identity performance: A case study of Chinese business people in Australia

Article

Source: OAI

CITATIONS

4

READS

297

2 authors:

Shuang Liu

The University of Queensland

68 PUBLICATIONS 960 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

P. E. Louw

The University of Queensland

91 PUBLICATIONS 863 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Cultural Translation and Identity Performance: A Case of Chinese Business People in Australia

Shuang Liu & Eric Louw
The University of Queensland

Abstract: This study investigates the interdependency of economic, socio-cultural and individual aspects of the identity negotiation experience of Chinese business people in Brisbane, Australia. Findings from semi-structured interviews conducted with 30 Chinese business owners indicated that their ability to translate between cultures and their competency of performing identities according to situational variations played a critical role in sustaining their ethnic business. Many Chinese ethnic business people are successful not because they fully assimilate themselves into the mainstream culture, but in fact, their success resides in the ability to live across two cultures and translate between them. The implication for policy makers is to create a social environment where migrants feel free to translate between cultures, rather than feeling pressured to either ground themselves in ethnic enclaves or to assimilate into the mainstream culture. [China Media Research. 2009; 5(1): 1-9]

Key words: Chinese; Cultural translation; Ethnic business; Identity; Migrants

Introduction

Increasing levels of immigration is the most significant contributor to the multicultural environment of Australia (DIMA, 2007a). As Castles pointed out, nowhere is this more apparent than in Australia where “immigration has always been a central part of nation building” (1992, p. 549). Since the end of World War II, approximately 6.5 million migrants have settled in Australia (DIMA, 2007c). Today, about 25 per cent of the population was born overseas and 200 languages are spoken in the country (DIMA, 2007b). Among these waves of migrant settlers are Chinese business people. Some of them set up their own small businesses because their qualifications made it hard for them to compete with the locals in the job market. Others, particularly those who migrated under the skilled stream, wanted to use their proven business attributes in the home country to develop business activities in their host country (DIMA, 2005). These Chinese business people face the task of moving between their ethnic group and the mainstream Anglo-Celtic cultural group to develop business operations and to maintain clientele in the host country (Collins, 2000; Dyer & Ross, 2000). As this move between host and home cultures involves selection and adaptation, we refer to it as cultural translation. For Chinese business people, cross cultural adaptation is not only a reconciliation of sometimes incompatible pressures for assimilation into the mainstream cultural group and differentiation from it, but it also involves economic survival in the host country. Part of this survival technique is learning the art of cultural translation.

A considerable amount of research has investigated cross-cultural adaptation of ethnic groups in Australia and beyond (e.g. Bruton, Ahlstrom & Wan, 2003; Leung, Pe-Pua & Karnilowicz, 2006; Liu, 2006; Ting-Toomey et al., 2000). However, the research on ethnic

business people has predominantly investigated business start-ups, explaining why and how members of various ethnic groups create new businesses (e.g. Aldrich & Waldinger, 1990; Collins, 2002; Dyer & Ross, 2000). A relatively small amount of research explores the rich complexity of the identity negotiation that ethnic entrepreneurs experience as they learn to move across cultural boundaries in order to sustain their businesses (Ang, 2000; Pécoud, 2004). Moreover, while existing studies have largely focused on the lives of migrants at the group level and arrived at generalisations applicable to different ethnic communities (Stodolska & Santos, 2006), they have not given sufficient attention to how identity negotiation is related to sustaining ethnic business over time.

This study aims to fill a gap by exploring the interdependency of economic, socio-cultural and individual aspects of the identity negotiation experience of Chinese business people in Australia and how this experience has impacted building “relationships in which other social actors cooperate” (Seltsikas & Lybereas, 1996, p. 33). ‘Chinese business people’ refers to migrants from mainland China, Hong Kong, Taiwan, Singapore and Malaysia, all of whom have a Chinese origin and speak Chinese (Mandarin or Cantonese). The rationale for choosing the Chinese ethnic group is based on their large cultural distance from Anglo-Celtic Australians (Nesdale, 2002) as well as their relative success in Australia (Collins, 1998). The Chinese community stands out as an out-group in relation to Anglo-Celtic Australians in terms of differences in culture and physical appearance. Cultural distance is related to the level of acceptance or prejudice from members of the cultural majority (Ho, Niles, Penny & Thomas, 1994; Marden & Mercer, 1998). Despite the ordeals faced by many Chinese-Australian business people due to stereotypes, prejudice, or even racism,

many of them have succeeded in creating viable businesses, jobs and community leadership (Collins, 2002). Thus, in view of the contributions of Chinese ethnic businesses to the Australian economy, research that enhances our understanding of the underlying dynamics of Chinese ethnic businesses has profound social significance.

Chinese Ethnic Business in Australia

While the Asian groups predominantly arrived in Australia after the abolition of the White Australia policy in the 1970s, Chinese migrants first came to Australia in as early as the gold rush era between 1851 and 1860 (Ip, 2005). Some Chinese migrants came to Australia because it offered a better living environment than their home country; others came because they wanted to give their children a good education in an English speaking country to prepare their children for a globalised future; still others migrated to Australia to gain opportunities unavailable in their home country. Implanted into a “demographically multiethnic society with predominantly monoculture legal and political institutions based on Anglo-Celtic traditions” (Hibbins, 2005, p. 170), migrants in Australia dreamed of freedom to be their own boss, to have autonomy in their choice of work and hopefully to achieve prosperity (Collins et al., 1995). Small businesses, such as a take-away shop, coffee shop, grocery store, or trading company are considered paths to realise the dreams of freedom and financial security. In addition, ethnic business is an avenue through which migrants whose professional qualifications are not accepted in their host country could attain marginal middle class status (Auster & Aldrich, 1984). In recent years, another major source of Chinese business people in Australia has been migrants under the skilled stream, that is, experienced entrepreneurs with existing capital.

The most salient feature of business efforts by Chinese migrants is their dependence on an ethnic community for support from friends and relatives, the larger networks of ethnic community organizations including religious associations, co-ethnic suppliers and other small businesses (Light, 1972). Evidence from previous research identified social networks as a critical part of the entrepreneurial activities of immigrants in many countries (Light & Gold, 2000; Waldinger, Aldrich & Ward, 1990). In the case of Chinese business, building social networks aligns with particular values underpinning Confucian philosophy that focuses on connections, networks and relationships with other people, particularly people from ingroups. For instance, many Chinese ethnic business people reside and have their shops in suburbs densely populated by Chinese migrants. Residential concentration brings several advantages: an initial cushion of customers is available, and a number of agglomeration economies arise when

co-ethnics start business in the same area. Customers drawn to the area by one shop (e.g. fruit and vegetable shop) may stay to patronise the others (e.g. butcher's or seafood store). In Brisbane, for example, majority of Chinese migrants live in relatively newer or established suburbs like Sunnybank, Eight Miles Plains, Robertson, and Runcorn (ABS, 2001).

However, there can also be a negative aspect of residential concentration because it distances immigrants from participating fully in the host culture and society (Kempen & Ozuekren, 1998). Lack of mutual understanding due to less intergroup contact may lead to stereotyping and prejudice towards migrant groups. Thus, while some Chinese ethnic businesses are fully dependent on the ethnic niche, many others have gradually expanded their clientele to the mainstream markets over the years. During the intergroup contact, Chinese ethnic businessmen not only switch between languages but also switch between cultures. Hence, they function as cultural translators. As “translators” they are able to reap the financial rewards of being able to draw on a wider pool of resources. Also, as translators, they are able to control and manipulate communication exchanges to their own advantage, which can be turned into economic profits. In other words, adopting the role of ‘translator’ can be more effective and profitable than being an assimilationist. The question, then, is under what conditions ethnic identity and ethnic business do or do not reinforce each other.

Acculturation and Identity Negotiation

Like all migrants, ethnic business people have to experience acculturation in the host country. Acculturation refers to a process of various changes different cultural groups undergo when they are in contact over a period of time (Berry, Kalin & Taylor, 1977; Berry, 1990). For ethnic minorities, acculturation involves maintenance of their ethnic cultural identity as well as building relationships with the mainstream culture. Identity integration, then, involves the continuum of the voluntary-involuntary dimension and the continuum of a perceived intergroup acceptance-rejection dimension (Ting-Toomey et al., 2000). Central to this cultural identity integration process is the social aspects of the self and the extent to which individuals define themselves in terms of their relationships to ingroups and outgroups (Brewer & Gardner, 1996; Markus & Kitayama, 1991; Triandis et al., 1988). Connectedness to either their own ethnic group or the larger cultural group is not merely affiliation between the self and others, but also entails fundamental differences in the way the self is construed under different circumstances (Brewer, 1991; Triandis, 1989). Therefore, cultural identity is not an immutable entity that migrants have. Rather, it is something they perform in accordance with situational variations.

As ethnic business people move between the mainstream and their ethnic communities in the host country, they also move between high-status and low-status social groups. An important assumption of social identity theory is that membership in a high-status group is desirable because it may contribute to a positive social identity (Ellemers, Wilke & van Knippenberg, 1993). Conversely, membership in a low-status group may negatively affect group members' self-concept as well as the image that others may have of them. Therefore, to maintain a positive self-concept derived from a satisfying social identity, individuals who belong to a group of subordinate status may strive for a higher status by leaving their low status group (Tajfel, 1978). However, this strategy to upgrade status may not apply to ethnic business people. The running of their business requires them to maintain close ties with their ethnic group because bonds of solidarity within the ethnic community provide resources for business operations as they establish and develop their ethnic businesses (Dyer & Ross, 2000), even if this is sometimes a low status group. In addition, ethnic communities may be a source of intangible assets such as values, knowledge, and networks upon which ethnic business people may draw (Greene, 1997). On the other hand, running their business successfully also requires ethnic business people to strive for gaining admission to the (often higher status) mainstream cultural group because they need to learn the 'ropes' in the host country environment and expand their business to the mainstream market. Hence, a positive association with both the ingroup (their own ethnic group) and the outgroup (the host cultural group) is essential in sustaining business and clientele. The maintenance of this positive association with both camps (migrant and host cultural) requires ethnic business people to negotiate their identities in different contexts.

This study investigated how identity is negotiated under different contexts by conducting semi-structured interviews to Chinese business people in the city of Brisbane, the third largest city in Australia. Chinese settlers from China, Taiwan, Singapore, Hong Kong and Malaysia are among the top 15 settler countries in Australia (Passmore, 2006). Between 2000 and 2005, the total increase of the East Asian population alone in Australia rose by 17 per cent (from approximately 850,000 to 1 million). In comparison, the total Australian population grew by approximately 5 per cent (from 19.4 million to 20.3 million) during the same period (ABS 2005). These migrants tend to be concentrated in larger cities (Forrest & Dunn, 2007). For example, in Queensland, North East Asian Chinese alone account for 58,544 people; most of them reside in Brisbane (ABS, 2001). The Chinese Asian community, though relatively a small portion of the total Australian population (6 per cent), is among the largest non-

English speaking minority in Australia today (ABS, 2007).

Methodology

Participants and Procedures

Data was collected via semi-structured interviews with 30 small Chinese business owners operating within Brisbane. Small business was operationally defined as an enterprise that has no more than 20 employees. A two-stage sampling procedure that combined a cluster sampling with snowball sampling strategy was employed. Specifically, we started with a short list of potential respondents provided by business associations as well as advertisements printed in ethnic and community newspapers. From this list, we used cluster sampling to select respondents who represented heterogeneity in types of business (e.g. retail stores, service industry, and professionals) and demographic characteristics (e.g. gender, age, and length of stay in the host country). From this initial list, we used snowball sampling to expand the sample to 30 respondents. This sampling procedure maximised sample variation and allowed us to locate some typical cases to yield informative data. The interviews were conducted between August 2006 and January 2007 at a venue of the respondent's choice (e.g. in their shops, houses, or a coffee shop). The duration of interviews was from 30 minutes to one hour.

The pool of the 30 respondents consisted of 70 per cent males and 30 per cent females; approximately 43 per cent of them were middle-aged (41-50), the youngest being 21 and the oldest being over 60; the majority of the respondents (73 per cent) had university or postgraduate education; 81 per cent had lived in Australia for over 10 years, although all were born overseas; about 40 per cent of them lived in suburbs moderately populated by Chinese migrants; the majority of them (70 per cent) used English at work but almost all of them (93 per cent) spoke natives language at home. Their businesses covered 12 fields ranging from grocery stores, take-way shops, building material firm, import/export trading company, Chinese herbalist, jewellery design, migrant agency, real estate agency and retirement village. The smallest business had two employees and the largest one had 20+. Some businesses had existed for two years; others for over 20 years, with an average history of eight years. The net annual income (based on those who provided this information) ranged from A\$20,000 to over \$A100,000. Interestingly, when asked to indicate the source of their customers/clients, 60 per cent indicated they had local Australians or foreigners (non-Chinese) as regular clients; 30 per cent indicated Chinese as their main customers; the rest (10 per cent) indicated they had about 50 per cent Chinese and 50 per cent foreigners as clients. The composition of clientele, to some extent,

explained why English was the most frequently used language at work.

Interview Guide

The interview guide consisted of five domains: demographic information, advantages/disadvantages of running an ethnic business, ethnic identification, acculturation orientations, and factors for sustaining their ethnic businesses. Demographic information included sex, age, education, income, residential area, length of stay in Australia, place of birth, and language used at home and at work. In addition to asking respondents to identify advantages and disadvantages of running ethnic businesses in Australia, we also asked them to explain the major difficulties they encountered in running an ethnic business (e.g. What are some major difficulties that you encounter in running an ethnic business?). Ethnic identification addressed self-esteem (e.g. In general, do you feel your ethnic group is valued and respected by others?) and group identification (e.g. Do you feel the ethnic group you belong to is an important reflection of who you are?). Acculturation orientation addressed their attitudes toward assimilation, integration, separation and marginalisation (e.g. Do you feel it is important for you to be accepted both by your ethnic group and the mainstream Anglo-Australian group?). We also asked respondents to indicate what they believed as important factors for sustaining an ethnic business in Australia.

Data Analysis

With consent of respondents, the majority of interviews were audio-recorded and transcribed. For those interviews that were not recorded due to either technical problems or respondents' unwillingness (26 per cent), notes were taken and expanded at the earliest time possible after the interview. Data analysis focused on the respondents' comments about the role of ethnic identity in the management of their ethnic businesses. Particular attention was given to coding those comments about the negotiation of identities during the interactions with their own ethnic groups (intragroup) and host cultural group (intergroup) to uncover patterns of strategies for the construction of self in different social situations. There was only one coder of the interview data. However, to enhance the reliability and validity of the results and conclusions drawn from the findings, the researcher paid special attention to negative cases and cross checked with the research assistant who conducted most of the interviews about the interpretation of findings.

Results and Discussion

Translating Culture: A Necessity for Running the Ethnic Business

Many of the respondents consider their Chinese origin as both an advantage and a disadvantage in running an ethnic business in Australia. The major advantage of being Chinese is that it helps them to communicate with co-ethnic customers and build a business network with suppliers from their home country. This ability to speak both English and Chinese gives Chinese businesses a competitive advantage over Australian local businesses, particularly reflected in the field of real estate, migration agencies, import and export trading, and mortgage brokers.

Being bilingual gives me the advantage over locals in that I can communicate accurately the information to Chinese customers who want to study in Australia. I can also explain mortgage terms and conditions, almost all printed in English. Particularly with mortgage, if the client is Chinese, she would like to talk to me in Chinese. There is an element of emotion in doing business. (No. 14, migrant agent and mortgage broker)

While the ethnic origin has equipped Chinese migrants with specific skills to attract local patrons (e.g. take-away shop supplying special food that locals cannot cook), the ethnic origin is also a barrier to their business because their non-native English speaker status and their ethnic cultural background prevent them from engaging in meaningful conversations with locals, i.e. conversation beyond weather and sports. Due to a lack of mutual understanding and stereotypes about the types of business Chinese or Asians do (e.g. restaurants or groceries stores) and their products (e.g. Products made in China are of medium or low quality.), it is difficult for Chinese ethnic businesses to make their mark in markets such as high quality building materials, jewellery design or furniture. An owner of the timber flooring company told us,

People have stereotypical beliefs about what kind of business Chinese can do. They don't trust our ability in this business [timber flooring]. It is not just Australian culture, but the Australian business culture that we need to understand more. (No. 13, owner of timber flooring company).

To compensate for these constraints and to compete with local businesses, Chinese shop owners tend to work for long hours (e.g. opening their shops seven days instead of six days per week). One respondent commented that whereas a Chinese person would sacrifice his or her family to make money, an Australian or Westerner would not put earning money above living life.

Another common strategy used to combat language and cultural difference is to hire locals, particularly at the beginning stage of the business to build up customer confidence and to bridge the cultural divide.

We are afraid Australians would question the authenticity of Western food prepared by Asians. Thus, at the beginning we employed some Australians. When customers feel our food is good, they come back. We also add some Asian food concept Australians can accept and appreciate. We have turned disadvantage [ethnic origin] into advantage. (No. 22, owner of a fast food shop)

The jewellery designer interviewed also related a similar experience. According to him, jewellery design is not considered a typical Chinese business. Initially local customers often questioned whether it was true that he himself designed the jewellery in the shop. Thus he had to hire a local Australian to sell his products.

Westerners like things appealing to the eye, a sense of freshness, whereas Asians like products that are durable. I combine my sense of beauty and theirs together. That's why locals say my design is 'different'. However, I have to hire a Westerner to sell my products. If a Chinese was to sell the goods, people [local Australians] would feel strange. They don't believe Chinese can design jewellery. In Western countries, you must find Westerners to promote the sale -- the correct channel to persuade people to buy (No. 12, fashion jewelry designer and shop owner).

Employing locals is a tactic for learning local cultural practices. Once Chinese businessmen have learned local practices and discourses they can perform roles in accordance with local stereotypes. But until they know how to successfully 'translate' between the Chinese and Australian cultures, they need someone else to perform that role for them.

Performing Identities: A Necessity for Sustaining the Ethnic Business

Ethnic businesses often belong to large, loosely interconnected networks of firms that prefer to conduct business with one another (Bruton, et al., 2003; Kao, 1993). Evidence from previous research identified social networks of ethnic entrepreneurs in many countries as a critical part of the business activities of immigrants (Light & Gold, 2000; Waldinger et al., 1990). Many respondents indicate they have suppliers/manufacturers in China. Friends and relatives also play a key role in finding financial resources. This connection with local and overseas Chinese functions as a unique social capital and a competitive advantage over local businesses.

Australians cannot compete with us regarding speed of information from overseas. When the local companies are still considering the deal, we are already loading the ship. Our advantage is quick information from home country [exporting country]. We are familiar with the ways of doing business there. Thus we can grab business opportunities. (No. 04, owner of seafood trading company)

This dependence on co-ethnic networks, to some extent, explains why many respondents prefer to reside in suburbs densely populated by Chinese migrants. The presence of an immigrant population creates a context in which they do not feel marginalised and are more confident in their relationship to members of the majority. Culturally and socially, residential concentration or ethnic enclaves also play an important role in facilitating cross cultural adaptation. A number of previous researchers found migrants prefer to live in ethnic enclaves as they strengthen social ties by maintaining cultural and religious practices (Alba, Logan & Crowder, 1997; Dunn, 1998). Social contacts in ethnic enclaves provide the continual survival of the home culture not existing within the norms and values of the host society (Kempen & Ozuekren, 1998). In Greve and Saliff's study (2005), they found that residing close to those who share the same cultural background help migrants to create affiliations, and thus enhances their social capital.

However, while taking advantage of the ethnic niche, many Chinese ethnic businesses endeavour to expand their business to the mainstream markets. To attract local customers, Chinese business people need to move between two ends of the acculturation continuum, i.e. maintaining ties with their ethnic culture and integrating into the host culture. Consequently, they need to perform identities according to situational characteristics. The ability to use ethnic resources while simultaneously achieving a distance to their ethnic group is an essential competence for running the ethnic business. Those who perform well achieve success. As one respondent put it,

Doing business here, we should integrate into the local, following their habits; however, we need to keep our own style but not stay too far away from the mainstream. (No. 28 owner of take away shop)

If identity negotiation involves coming to terms with the changing self (Hall 1996), then which self-category becomes salient and at which level of abstraction is a function of an interaction between the characteristics of the person and the characteristics of the situation (Piontkowski, Florack, Hoelker & Obdrzalek, 1999; Turner, 1987).

It is important for us to be accepted by both our ethnic group and the Australian society. For survival, we need to be accepted by the mainstream. However, we should keep our own cultural characteristics; then we won't lose ourselves. (No. 24, real estate agent)

While being aware of the need to be accepted by the larger culture, most respondents feel the ethnic group they belong to is an important reflection of who they are. At home, they mostly speak native language (Mandarin or Cantonese). They want their offspring to learn their mother tongue and achieve well in education.

They hope that by learning the native language, their children will acquire particular traditional values and therefore tradition can be protected through the language. At societal level, they maintain contacts with friends and families abroad as well as develop ties within migrant community in the host country. These cultural activities are a natural extension of their lives from the home country (Stodolska & Santos, 2006).

When asked about their attitudes towards integrating into the larger culture, many respondents expressed doubt about assimilation. In the first place, their physical appearance sets them apart from the Anglo-Celtic Australians. Additionally, they are clearly aware that their roots are in China.

On the surface level, it is easy to assimilate into the host country's way of living and working. However, the way of thinking can never be assimilated. We are heavily influenced by Confucianism. There can only be a limited level of assimilation (No. 1, owner of convenience store).

Most respondents feel they only need to act like an Australian rather than trying to be an Australian. As a gift shop owner said, 'If you are in a flock of sheep, you need to look like a sheep. If you are among a group of ducks, you need to look like a duck' (No. 2, owner of gift shop). Similar remarks were made by another respondent,

Do as the Romans do when you are in Rome. We are the minority; cannot compare with the majority. We should understand and recognise mainstream culture but we don't have to try hard to learn the mainstream culture. (No. 7, Asian groceries store)

This requires learning the art of 'translation' sufficiently well to successfully straddle the cultural boundary. Cultural identity, then, is not something they have, but something they perform.

We can get into close contact with the locals but not assimilate. The mainstream makes policies. Chinese must abide by those policies. Living here, we need to take into consideration the local factors. However, the Chinese are forever Chinese (No. 16, owner of furniture and electric appliances store).

The astute Chinese business people have realised that actual assimilation (i.e. totally reconstructing oneself in accordance with the host culture's discourses and practices) would entail the loss of something valuable, namely the ability to function simultaneously within two different cultures. Thus, they derive benefit from adopting a strategy of deliberate cultural dualism – they perform a constructed identity that mainstream Australian culture finds acceptable and simultaneously perform an in-house (Chinese) identity when dealing with Chinese-in-Australia and Chinese contacts overseas. The result can be a very complex mixture of performing differential status roles, social rules and value-systems. This competency of performing different

identities in different contexts makes them a cultural translator. Being able to translate between these two different worlds generates a range of business opportunities not available to those who are mono-cultural.

Conclusion

Migration means having to learn to deal with two different cultures – one's original culture and the host culture one has migrated to. Consequently, migrants engage in communication with three types of audience: members of the mainstream culture, people from the home country, and their children who grow up in a new culture.

Firstly, migrants have to learn how to communicate with members of the dominant culture in the host country. This involves learning about a new culture and the practices and discourses of this host culture. They face a choice of how to respond to the new culture they encounter, namely: (a) they can allow themselves to be assimilated into the new culture; (b) they can opt to minimise their engagement with the new culture by withdrawing into a (migrant) cultural enclave; (c) they can develop the skills of operating simultaneously in two different cultures and of effectively "translating" between the two cultures.

Secondly, migrants must (re)learn how to communicate with people from the home country. Engaging with the original culture can take three forms, namely: (a) migrants can keep in regular contact with people from the home country. This means the migrant effectively remains a "part" of the original cultural formation, albeit as a diasporic member. If the migrant opts for this route, s/he will effectively find himself or herself living within two cultures and therefore constantly "translating" between these two cultures; but this still involves learning a new form of communicating with those in the home country. (b) Migrants can lose touch with the home country. If this happens they will eventually only have a "historical" understanding of the home country, and they will lose the ability to translate between the two cultures. (c) Migrants can maintain partial contact with the home country. If this happens their 'translation' abilities will be impaired because they will gradually lose touch with ongoing developments and shifts in their original culture.

Thirdly, migrants have to learn to "translate" between their home culture and their children's hybridised culture. Learning to cope with their children's hybridised culture and possibly learning to deploy this knowledge within the "translation" work is a part of their daily routine.

This study has explored the experience of Chinese ethnic business people as cultural translators and how the competency of translating between cultures relates to their economic survival.

Ethnic business people are unable to move away from ethnic enclaves due to their dependence on co-ethnic networks as social capital. Chinese business people in Australia appear to have discovered that maintaining on-going contact with the home country/culture has distinct economic benefits. Thus, to run their ethnic business, they need to maintain sufficient contact with the home culture so as to keep up to date with cultural shifts in the home country; and thereby be able to pass themselves off as still a member of the Chinese cultural formation when conducting business with people in the home country. However, Chinese ethnic business people are fully aware of the need to consciously shape the cultural dimension of their business and to target a non-ethnic clientele (Pécoud, 2004). Whether they enjoy engaging with people from the mainstream cultural background or not, they need to do so for economic reasons. The implications for Chinese business people in Australia are that assimilation would be counterproductive. But withdrawing into Chinese enclaves in the host country is also counterproductive. The most profitable response would be to learn the art of “translation,” i.e. to select and adapt according to contexts. When home and host cultures coexist without merging, people may develop the ability to cross cultural boundaries and to move from one cultural milieu to another without feeling disoriented.

In our study, the Chinese ethnic business people seem to have tried to learn enough about the local dominant discourses and practices to enable them to convincingly perform the identity that Australians would find “acceptable.” This means performing to Australian stereotypes about “Chinese,” but simultaneously appearing to integrate into the Australian nation. At the same time, they maintain an ongoing and strong link with their original Chinese cultural formations to enable them to perform appropriate identity in the home country. In other words, learning the arts of intercultural translation best equips migrants in ethnic businesses. Our findings indicate that the ability to translate between cultures play an important role in running and sustaining ethnic businesses. However, such competencies do not come naturally, but have to be learned.

The Australian government, like many Western governments, increasingly views migration through an economic lens, arguing that skilled professionals achieve the best employment outcomes and therefore constitute the ideal migrants (Ho, 2006). As a result, large numbers of migrants are being attracted to Australia to meet the demands of a growing economy. But at the same time there is a growing feeling of unease in some host nationals that migration policies are leading to the growth of migrant enclaves that refuse to assimilate into the mainstream culture. The results of our research revealed that many ethnic businesses are

precisely successful because they do not fully assimilate themselves into the mainstream culture. In fact, their success is born of the ability to live “across” two cultures and “translate” between them. The implications of this for migration policy are significant. On the one hand, the economic imperatives underpinning migration policy should not allow migrants to form themselves in (non-assimilable) ethnic enclaves. On the other hand, there is a need not to pressure migrants to assimilate into the mainstream culture. For migration policy makers this may be an issue worthy of consideration.

Correspondence to:

Dr. Shuang Liu
School of Journalism and Communication
The University of Queensland
Brisbane, QLD 4072
Tel: (07) 3365 3070
Email: s.liu1@uq.edu.au

References

- Alba, R. D., Logan, J. R., & Crowder, K. (1997). White ethnic neighbourhoods and assimilation. *Social Forces*, 75(3), 883-912.
- Aldrich, H. & Waldinger, R. (1990). Ethnicity and entrepreneurship. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 16, 111-135.
- Ang, I. (2000). Transforming Chinese identities in Australia: between assimilation, multiculturalism, and diaspora. In T. A. See (Ed.), *Intercultural relations, cultural transformation, and identity* (pp. 248-258). Manila: Kaisa Para Sa Kaunlaran, Inc.
- Auster, E. & Aldrich, H. (1984). Small business vulnerability, ethnic enclaves and ethnic enterprise. In R. Ward & R. Jenkins (Eds.), *Ethnic communities in business* (pp. 39-54). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- ABS (Australian Bureau of Statistics) (2001) Brisbane a Social Atlas. [Online] Accessed 22 August 2006 at <http://www.abs.gov.au/AUSSTATS/abs@nsf/DetailsPage/2030.32001?OpenDocument>.
- ABS (Australian Bureau of Statistics) (2005) Year Book Australia 2005. [Online] Accessed 2 October 2006 at <http://www.abs.gov.au/AUSSTATS/abs@nsf/Lookup/6A5AABD7621230ADCA256F7200832F77>.
- ABS (Australian Bureau of Statistics) (2007) Year Book Australia 2007. <http://www.abs.gov.au/AUSSTATS/abs@nsf/Detailspage/1301.02007?OpenDocument>, accessed 2 May 2007.
- Berry, J. (1990). Psychology of acculturation: Understanding individuals moving between cultures. In R. Brislin (Ed.), *Applied Cross-cultural Psychology* (pp. 232-253). Newbury Par, CA: Sage.
- Berry, J., Kalin, R., & Taylor, D. (1977). *Multiculturalism and ethnic attitudes in Canada*.

- Ottawa: Ministry of Supply and Services.
- Brewer, M. B. (1991). The social self: On being the same and different at the same time. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 17, 475-482.
- Brewer, M. B. & Gardner, W. (1996). Who is this "We"? Levels of collective identity and self representations. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 71(1), 83-93.
- Bruton, G. D., Ahlstrom, D., & Wan, J. C. (2003). Turnaround in East Asian firms: Evidence from ethnic overseas Chinese communities. *Strategic Management Journal*, 24: 519-540.
- Castles, S. (1992). The Australian model of immigration and multiculturalism: Is it applicable to Europe? *International Immigration Review*, 26(2), 549-567.
- Collins, J. (1998). Immigrant unemployment and ethnic small business in Australia. In E. Carson, A. Jamrozic & T. Winefield (Eds.), *Unemployment: Economic promise and political will* (pp. 133-147). Brisbane Academic Press.
- Collins, J. (2000). Ethnicity, gender and Australian entrepreneurs: Rethinking Marxist views on small business. *Journal of Social Change and Critical Inquiry*, 2, 1-27.
- Collins, J. (2002). Chinese entrepreneurs: The Chinese diaspora in Australia. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour and Research*, 8: 113-133.
- Collins, J., Gibson, K., Alcorso, C., Castles, S., & Tait, D. (1995). *Shop Full of dreams—Ethnic small business in Australia*. Sydney: Pluto Press Australia.
- DIMA (Department of Immigration and Multicultural and Indigenous Affairs) (2005) *Business Skills Program*. [Online] Accessed 8 November 2005 at <http://www.immi.gov.au/facts/27business.htm>.
- DIMA (Department of Immigration and Multicultural Affairs) (2007a). *Fact Sheet 6: The Evolution of Australia's Multicultural Policy*. [Online] Accessed 19 January 2007 at <http://www.dimia.gov.au/media/fact-sheets/06evolution.html>.
- DIMA (Department of Immigration and Multicultural Affairs) (2007b). *Fact Sheet 8: Abolition of the 'White Australia' Policy*. [Online] accessed 19 January 2007 at <http://www.dimia.gov.au/media/fact-sheets/08abolition.html>.
- DIMA (Department of Immigration and Multicultural Affairs) (2007c). *Fact Sheet 4: More Than 60 Years of Post War Migration*. [Online] accessed 19 January 2007 at <http://www.dimia.gov.au/media/fact-sheets/04fifty.html>.
- Dunn, K. M. (1998). Rethinking ethnic concentration: The case of Cabramatta, Sydney. *Urban Studies*, 35(3), 503-527.
- Dyer, C. & Ross, C. A. (2000). Ethnic enterprises and their clientele. *Journal of Business Management*, 38(2): 48-78.
- Ellemers, N, Wilke, H., & van Knippenberg, A. (1993). Effects of the legitimacy of low group of individual status on individual and collective status-enhancement strategies. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 64(5), 766-778.
- Forrest, J. & Dunn, K. (2007). Constructing racism in Sydney, Australia's largest ethnicity. *Urban Studies*, 44(4): 699-721.
- Greene, P. (1997). A resource-based approach to ethnic business sponsorship: A consideration of Ismaili-Pakistani immigrants. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 35, 58-71.
- Greve, A. & Salaff, J. W. (2005). Social network approach to understand the ethnic economy: A theoretical discourse. *GeoJournal*, 64(1), 7-16.
- Hall, S. (1996). Who needs identity. In S. Hall & P. de Gay (Eds.), *Questions of cultural identity* (pp. 1-17). London: Sage.
- Hibbins, R. (2005). Migration and gender identity among Chinese skilled male migrants to Australia. *Geoforum*, 36: 167-180.
- Ho, C. (2006). Migration as Feminisation? Chinese women's experiences of work and family in Australia. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 32, 497-514.
- Ho, R., Niles, S., Penny, R., & Thomas, A. (1994). Migrants and multiculturalism—a survey of attitudes in Darwin. *Australian Psychologist*, 29: 62-70.
- Ip, D. (2005). Contesting Chinatown: Place-making and the emergence of "ethnoburbia" in Brisbane, Australia. *GeoJournal*, 64, 63-74.
- Kao, J. (1993). The worldwide web of Chinese business. *Harvard Business Review*, 71(2), 24-36.
- Kempen, V. R. & Ozuekren, A. S. (1998). Ethnic segregation in cities: New forms and explanations in a dynamic world. *Urban Studies*, 35(10), 1631-1656.
- Leung, C., Pe-Pua, R., & Karnilowicz, W. (2006). Psychological adaptation and autonomy among adolescents in Australia: A comparison of Anglo-Celtic and three Asian groups. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 30(1): 99-118.
- Light, I. (1972). *Ethnic enterprise in America: Business and Welfare among Chinese, Japanese, and Blacks*. Berkeley, CA: University of California Press.
- Light, I. & Gold, S. J. (2000). *Ethnic Economies*. San Deigo, CA: Academic Press.
- Liu, S. (2006). An examination of the effects of print media exposure and contact on subjective social reality and acculturation attitudes. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 30, 365-382.
- Marden, P. & Mercer, D. (1998). Locating strangers: multiculturalism, citizenship and nationhood in Australia. *Political Geography*, 17(8), 939-958.
- Markus, H. & Kitayama, S. (1991). Culture and the self: Implications for cognition, emotion, and motivation.

- Psychological Review*, 98, 224-253.
- Nesdale, D. (2002). Acculturation attitudes and the ethnic and host-country identification of immigrants. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 32(7), 1488-1507.
- Passmore, D. (2006). The new arrivals changing our lives. *The Sunday Mail*, 29 October, 54-55.
- Pécoud, A. (2004). Entrepreneurship and identity: Cosmopolitanism and cultural competencies among German-Turkish businesspeople in Berlin. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 30(1), 3-20.
- Piontkowski, U., Florack, A., Hoelker, P., & Obdrzalek, P. (2000). Predicting acculturation attitudes of dominant and non-dominant groups. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 24 (1), 1-26.
- Seltsikas, P. & Lybereas, T. (1996). The culture of entrepreneurship: Towards a relational perspective. *Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship*, 13, 25-36.
- Stodolska, M. & Santos, C. A. (2006) "You must think of Familia": The everyday lives of Mexican migrants in destination communities. *Social & Cultural Geography*, 7(4): 627-647.
- Tajfel, H. (1978). *The social psychology of minorities*. New York: Minority Rights Group.
- Ting-Toomey, S., Yee-Jung, K. K., Shapiro, R. B., Garcia, W, Wright, T. J., & Oetzel, J. G. (2000). Ethnic/cultural identity salience and conflict styles in four US ethnic groups. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 24(1), 47-81.
- Triandis, H. C. (1989). The self and social behavior in differing cultural contexts. *Psychological Review*, 60, 649-655.
- Triandis, H. C., Bontempo, R., Villareal, M., Asai, M., & Lucca, N. (1988). Individualism and collectivism: Cross-cultural perspectives on self-ingroup relationships. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 54, 323-338.
- Turner, J. C. (1987). *Rediscovering the social group: A self-categorization theory*. Oxford: Basil Blackwell.
- Waldinger, R., Aldrich, H., & Ward, R. (1990). *Ethnic Entrepreneurs*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.